

Potassium for Yield Improvement of Wheat

ASHOK TIWARI*, K. N TIWARI and A N PATHAK

Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, C. S Azad University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur-208 002

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A large scale deficiency of potassium in soils of Uttar Pradesh was reported much earlier¹. The situation appears to have been aggravated further because of depletion of soil potassium in consequence to exhaustive cropping². Available K content of soil, magnitude of equilibrium among different forms and mineralogical composition of soil dictate the increase in yield due to added potassium³. Soon after the introduction of high yielding varieties of cereals during the mid-sixties, responses to added K were evidenced in a larger number of experiments conducted on cultivator's fields in Uttar Pradesh⁴. All these evidences stress upon judicious use of K for sustained productivity. The importance of soil testing is often emphasised for profitable fertiliser use, but unfortunately fertiliser particularly K is being used without taking into account the available K status of soil which ultimately influences the profitability of potassium use. In view of paucity of information on soil test-crops response correlation studies on potassium, the present inves-

tigation was planned to evaluate responses of wheat to potassium application in soils of varying potassium fertility status.

Results and Discussion

Crop response to potassium : The responses to added K varied in accordance with the available K status of soils, being larger in soils testing low and vice versa. Increase in grain yields due to added K was significant in soils having NH₄OAc extractable K upto 94 ppm. The available K being increased beyond this level the increase in the yield was non-significant (Table 1).

Interestingly, the magnitude of response to added K at similar available K status differed in accordance with the non-exchangeable K (boiling 1 N HNO₃ extractable K) content of soils. The smaller the amount of non-exchangeable K content of the soil larger was the response to added K. Responses to K in 3 out of 7 sites

TABLE 1—RELATIONSHIP OF AVAILABLE K STATUS OF SOILS AND Q/I PARAMETERS WITH RESPONSE OF WHEAT TO ADDED K

Site no	Initial K status (ppm)				Q/I parameters			Grain Yield				CD 5%
	Water soluble K	Available K (NH ₄ OAc extr K)	HNO ₃ extr K	HCl extr K	AR ₀ ^k (M/L) ^{1/2}	KL (me/100 g)	PBC ^k (me/100 g) (M/L) ^{1/2}	0	25	50	75	
1	41	68	1400	1868	0.0036	0.30	33.3	3554	3954	4283	4137	275
2	16	74	901	2028	0.0040	0.35	32.5	3894	4165	4583	4308	278
3	20	78	1319	2145	0.0040	0.40	35.0	4661	5017	4884	4784	268
4	39	78	757	2085	0.0040	0.43	27.5	3330	3663	3956	3838	259
5	20	90	757	2098	0.0050	0.45	30.0	3461	3751	3792	3663	238
6	20	94	620	2051	0.0057	0.47	20.3	3453	4031	4237	4153	320
7	39	113	776	1927	0.0025	0.42	40.0	3754	3939	3964	3888	NS

were significant upto 50 kg ha⁻¹, in 3 sites only upto 25 kg ha⁻¹, and in one site which contained available K more than 100 ppm, the increase in grain yield was non-significant. A large number of experiments conducted on cultivators' fields all over the country have shown significant increase in yield of wheat to added K. The time series data for the response of wheat to 60 kg K₂O per hectare over N₁₂₀P₆₀ summarised by Bhargava *et al.*⁵ clearly showed that at 60 kg K₂O per hectare level, the increase in yield was about 6–10 kg grain kg⁻¹ of applied nutrient during 1977-78 as against 2–4 kg grain in the early period. Tiwari *et al.*⁶ observed a clear relationship between available K status of the soil and response of wheat to its application. Application of 60 kg K₂O per hectare improved the wheat yield, the magnitude of response being larger in increasing extent of K deficiency. Kapur *et al.*⁷ while studying the responses to K application in soils of varying available K status of Jalandhar (Punjab), recommended for application of 90 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ in soils testing low and 60 kg K₂O per hectare in medium and high K soils.

Quantity-intensity parameters : The quantity-intensity parameters also showed good relationship with responses to added K (Table 1). The *Q/I* parameters for two selected sites (responsive and

Fig. 1. *Q/I* parameters of soil having NH₄OAc extractable K, 68 ppm.

Fig. 2. *Q/I* parameters of soil having NH₄OAc extractable K, 113 ppm.

non-responsive) are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. Soils responding to added potassium had relatively low PBC^K and high AR₀^K. The labile K (K_L) contents of responsive soils were lower than those of non-responsive soil. A high PBC^K is preferred for continued and sustained supply of K from soil. Similar observations were made by Tiwari⁸ for Indian soils growing wheat.

Experimental

Seven scientifically designed experiments were conducted on cultivators' fields in Rarha soil series of district Kanpur 'Dehat' to evaluate the responses of wheat variety HD-1553 to K application. Selection of the fields was done on the basis of predetermined available K status of soils. The experiments were conducted in randomised block design with four levels of K (0, 25, 50 and 75 kg ha⁻¹) applied through muriate of potash with four replicates in each case. Nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P₂O₅) were applied at the rate of 120 and 60 kg ha⁻¹ respectively through urea and diammonium phosphate taking into account the supply of N through latter. Sowing was done in the third week of November 1985 and irrigation and cultural operations were done timely to maintain ideal conditions as far as practical. After harvest of the crop, grain and straw yields were recorded. Initial soil samples

NOTE

were analysed for their K content using four extractants, viz distilled water, 1 N NH₄OAc (exchangeable), HNO₃ (non-exchangeable) and HCl (lattice-K) and *Q/I* parameters by the reported procedures⁹

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